

Management Strategies and Challenges Associated with Pancreatic Pseudocysts in a Tertiary Care Environment

Kamlesh Vegad¹, Mukesh Chande², Rajesh Gouri³, Harsh Sheth⁴

^{1,2}Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj, Kutch, Gujarat, India

³Professor and Head, Department of General Surgery, Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj, Kutch, Gujarat, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj, Kutch, Gujarat, India

Received: 18-08-2024 / Revised: 21-09-2024 / Accepted: 16-01-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Harsh Sheth

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aim: Pancreatic pseudo cysts may develop as a result of either acute or chronic pancreatitis. The comprehension of pseudo cysts has evolved over time, driven by advancements in radiology and the emergence of new treatment options. This study seeks to evaluate the range of diagnostic and therapeutic options for intervention, as well as to assess the effectiveness of various management strategies for pseudocysts.

Material and Methods: A total of 40 cases were examined, each presenting with either palpable or non-palpable abdominal lumps. These cases raised clinical suspicion of pancreatic pseudocysts, which were subsequently confirmed through ultrasound or CT scans of the abdomen, revealing fluid associated with the pancreas. A total of 28 patients received conservative management, while surgical intervention was performed on the remaining 12 patients.

Results: The findings indicate that the predominant risk factor for pancreatic pseudocysts was alcohol-induced pancreatitis, observed in 28 patients (70%). This was followed by gallstone-induced pancreatitis, which was present in 7 patients (17.5%). Abdominal pain emerged as the most prevalent symptom, affecting 36 patients, or 90% of the cohort. This was closely followed by anorexia, reported in 30 patients, accounting for 75% of those studied. Among the 40 patients studied, 9 experienced complications related to pancreatic pseudocysts. In three cases, representing 7.5%, there was a presence of infected pseudocyst and pleural effusion. Among the 28 patients who received conservative treatment, 14 individuals (50%) experienced complete resolution of the pseudocyst. In contrast, 7 patients (25%) showed no change in the size of the cyst, while another 7 patients (25%) exhibited an increase in the size of the pancreatic pseudocyst.

Conclusion: Pseudocyst of the pancreas is primarily observed in males, with alcohol consumption identified as the most prevalent contributing factor. The most frequent site is near the head of the pancreas, where abdominal pain often serves as the initial symptom, accompanied by an abdominal lump as a notable clinical sign.

Keywords: Anorexia, Gall stone, Pancreas, Pseudocyst.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The pancreas is often regarded as one of the most challenging organs in the human body, prompting many surgeons to refrain from even examining it unless absolutely required. Its retroperitoneal position contributes to its enigmatic nature, making it a less understood organ in medical discussions. Acute pancreatitis is typically marked by a sudden emergence of symptoms in an otherwise healthy person, with those symptoms subsiding as the episode resolves. In contrast, individuals with chronic pancreatitis may have experienced prior episodes or exhibit signs of exocrine or endocrine

insufficiency before the current episode, and their symptoms can linger even after the current episode has resolved. Recent advancements have led to a clearer differentiation of complications associated with pancreatitis, such as peripancreatic effusions, acute pseudocyst formation, and pancreatic necrosis. The capacity to examine these lesions noninvasively at various intervals has facilitated the differentiation between acute and chronic pseudocysts, two entities that may appear similar yet possess markedly different natural histories and treatment needs. [1,2,3] Pseudocysts typically emerge after an

episode of acute pancreatitis, but they can also form in cases of chronic pancreatitis or as a result of pancreatic injury. [4] It is essential to distinguish this from peripancreatic fluid collections, which are commonly observed during the acute phase of acute pancreatitis. The majority of these cases resolve by the fourth week of illness, although a small percentage may persist and develop into pseudocysts. [5] The development of a pseudocyst typically takes at least four weeks following an episode of acute pancreatitis. During this period, the surrounding inflammation evolves, accompanied by pancreatic secretions and granulation tissue, ultimately resulting in a distinct fibrous-walled collection. This process may occur with or without the rupture of a pancreatic duct. [6] Cysts of this nature typically diminish over time, although they may also remain as a collection that does not produce symptoms. In certain cases, a cyst may experience secondary infection, rupture, or exhibit internal bleeding as a result of pseudoaneurysm formation. This study seeks to evaluate the range of diagnostic and therapeutic approaches available for intervention, as well as to assess the effectiveness of various management strategies for pseudocysts.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted over the course of one year at a tertiary care hospital located in Gujarat, India. A total of 40 cases were examined, each presenting with either palpable or non-palpable abdominal lumps. These cases raised clinical suspicion of pancreatic pseudocysts, which were subsequently confirmed through ultrasound or CT scans of the abdomen, revealing fluid associated with the pancreas.

The study excluded all true pancreatic cysts, neoplastic cystic swellings, hydatid cysts, and congenital cysts identified through ultrasonography or CT imaging. The biochemical parameters assessed comprised total blood counts, serum amylase and lipase levels, blood sugar measurements, as well as evaluations of liver and kidney function. All patients underwent Ultrasonography and Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography.

A total of 28 patients received conservative management, while surgical intervention was performed on the remaining 12 patients. Conservative medical management involved the administration of analgesics, including opioids like Tramadol in either injection or tablet form, alongside non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, antiemetics, and intravenous fluids as needed, aimed at providing symptomatic relief for the patient's conditions. Patients receiving conservative management were monitored every 6-8 weeks throughout the study, utilising physical abdominal examinations and ultrasonography for assessment.

In cases where the cyst measured over 6 cm and exhibited a mature wall (with a thickness exceeding 6 mm, as identified through a Computed Tomography scan), direct intervention was undertaken without prior observation, adhering to the established criteria known as the "Rule of 6" (which pertains to pseudocysts larger than 6 cm, with wall thickness greater than 6 mm, and persisting for more than 6 weeks).

Statistical analysis

The collected data was organised and input into a spreadsheet application (Microsoft Excel 2019) before being transferred to the data editor interface of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were characterised using means and standard deviations or medians and interquartile ranges, depending on their distribution patterns. Qualitative variables were reported in terms of counts and percentages. In this study, the confidence level was established at 95%, while the level of significance was determined to be 5% for all tests conducted.

Results

The average age at which pancreatic pseudocysts occur is 35.70 ± 10.24 years, with a notable prevalence in individuals during their fourth decade of life. The prevalence of the disease was notably higher among males, accounting for 90% of cases. Alcohol-induced pancreatitis emerged as the predominant risk factor for pancreatic pseudocysts, affecting 28 patients (70%). This was followed by gallstone-induced pancreatitis, which was observed in 7 patients (17.5%).

Abdominal pain emerged as the most prevalent symptom, affecting 36 patients, or 90% of the cohort. This was closely followed by anorexia, reported in 30 patients, representing 75% of those studied. The study identified a palpable abdominal lump as the most prevalent clinical sign, observed in 19 patients (47.5%). This was closely followed by the presence of ascites in 13 patients (32.5%). A total of 27 patients, representing 67.5%, experienced pseudocyst formation associated with chronic pancreatitis, while 13 patients, or 32.5%, developed pseudocysts as a consequence of acute pancreatitis.

Among a cohort of 40 patients, 9 experienced complications stemming from pancreatic pseudocysts. In three cases, representing 7.5%, there was a presence of infected pseudocyst and pleural effusion. In a recent observation, the rupture of a pseudocyst in the abdominal cavity occurred in one patient, representing 2.5% of the cases. Additionally, another patient experienced a cystopleural fistula, also at a rate of 2.5%, which subsequently advanced to empyema of the left pleural cavity. A total of 28 patients, representing 70%, underwent conservative management, while

the remaining 12 patients received surgical intervention, as detailed in Table 1.

Four patients experienced residual postoperative pain lasting beyond 6 to 12 weeks following their surgical procedures, while three patients developed infections. The 28 patients who were managed conservatively underwent regular clinical assessments and ultrasonography follow-ups throughout the duration of this study. Among the 28 patients studied, 14 individuals (50%) experienced complete resolution of the pseudocyst. In contrast, 7

patients (25%) exhibited no change in the size of the cyst, while another 7 patients (25%) showed an increase in the size of the pancreatic pseudocyst.

Patients were monitored closely to determine any increase in size and changes in wall maturation, including wall thickness. If symptoms developed, an intervention was considered. This cohort of patients presented with pseudocysts exceeding 6cm in size, which has hindered the possibility of complete resolution.

Table 1: The management modalities used for treatment of pseudocyst of pancreas

Management	N=40	Percentage (%)
Conservative	28	70
Cysto-gastrostomy	7	17.5
ERCP Stenting	1	2.5
Pancreatic duct stenting with decortication of left pleura	1	2.5
Cysto-jejunostomy	1	2.5
Distal Pancreatectomy with excision of pseudocyst with Splenectomy	1	2.5
External Drainage	1	2.5

Discussion

A pseudocyst is characterised as a distinct fluid collection that lacks any associated tissue necrosis and persists for four weeks or longer following the onset of a disease. The formation of a pseudocyst necessitates an interruption in the pancreatic duct, typically arising from acute pancreatitis, trauma, or duct obstruction associated with chronic pancreatitis. [7,8]

Alcohol-induced pancreatitis emerged as the predominant risk factor for pancreatic pseudocysts, affecting 28 patients (70%), while gallstone-induced pancreatitis was noted in 7 patients (17.5%). A recent meta-analysis conducted by Samokhvalov et al highlights the crucial role of alcohol metabolism in health outcomes. The study reveals that this process is linked to the generation of reactive oxygen species through the acetaldehyde pathway, as well as the formation of fatty acid ethyl esters via a nonoxidative route. These biochemical changes can lead to damage in acinar cells and the activation of stellate cells, raising important concerns for overall health. [9]

In our study, 27 patients (67.5%) experienced pseudocyst formation associated with chronic pancreatitis, while 13 patients (32.5%) developed pseudocysts as a sequel to acute pancreatitis. A study conducted by Habashi et al. reveals that the formation of pseudocysts associated with pancreatitis appears to originate from disturbances in the pancreatic duct, which subsequently leads to the leakage of pancreatic secretions. [10] Approximately two-thirds of individuals diagnosed with pseudocysts exhibit identifiable links between the cyst and the pancreatic duct. This can manifest as an obstruction in a major branch of the pancreatic

duct, often caused by a protein plug, calculus, or localized fibrosis, which is commonly associated with chronic pancreatitis. In this condition, there is notable pancreatic parenchymal disease accompanied by multiple strictures throughout the pancreatic duct. Conversely, the remaining one-third of cases involve an inflammatory response occurring in the context of acute pancreatitis.

Alcohol stands out as the primary risk factor for both acute and chronic pancreatitis, which can lead to the formation of pseudocysts. Ascites was identified in 13 patients, accounting for 32.5% of the cases. A study conducted by Koide T et al outlines the dynamics of a cystopleural fistula, which primarily expands in two directions.

Anterior disruption of a pancreatic pseudocyst that drains into the peritoneal cavity can lead to the development of ascites. Conversely, posterior disruption may result in a retroperitoneal fistula that can extend inferiorly into the pelvis or superiorly through the oesophageal and/or aortic hiatus, ultimately reaching the thoracic cavity and typically presenting as a left pleural effusion. [11]

The preferred treatment for pancreatic pseudocysts is influenced by several factors, such as the size, quantity, and location of the pseudocysts; the status of the main pancreatic duct, whether it is obstructed or communicating with the pseudocyst; and the presence of any complications associated with the pseudocyst. The primary determinant influencing the choice of treatment is the availability of local expertise. [12] A total of 28 patients, representing 70%, were treated conservatively, resulting in complete resolution of the pseudocyst in 14 individuals. In the remaining patients, the cyst either maintained its size or exhibited a slight increase.

[12] Among the remaining 12 patients, 9 underwent open internal drainage, while 3 received endoscopic internal drainage along with pancreatic duct stenting. Additionally, one patient had external drainage performed, and another underwent distal pancreatic resection. A study conducted by Usatoff et al. reveals that pseudocysts persisting for over six weeks rarely resolve on their own. Furthermore, the likelihood of complications arising from pseudocysts in the context of chronic pancreatitis can reach up to 55%. [13]

A comprehensive population-based study involving 14,914 patients with pancreatic pseudocysts compared percutaneous drainage (n = 8121) to open surgical drainage (n = 6409). The findings indicated that those undergoing percutaneous drainage experienced a longer hospital stay and a mortality rate that was double that of the open surgical group (5.9% vs. 2.8%). [14] At present, the application of percutaneous or external pseudocyst drainage remains restricted, typically reserved for cases involving underlying medical issues or complications associated with the cyst. While there are numerous alternatives and less invasive methods available, it is crucial to highlight that the most effective and dependable treatment for a pseudocyst remains internal drainage through an open surgical procedure.

Therefore, early intervention is recommended for chronic pancreatic pseudocysts, with a strong expectation of identifying a mature cyst that can effectively hold sutures. Surgery remains the preferred approach for addressing unresolved and complicated pancreatic pseudocysts. The use of laparoscopic and endoscopic management has shown promising outcomes; however, long-term follow-up is essential to evaluate its effectiveness in comparison to traditional open techniques. [15]

Conclusion

Pseudocyst of pancreas is predominantly seen in males with alcohol consumption being the commonest etiological factor.

The commonest location is around the head of pancreas with abdominal pain as presenting symptom and abdominal lump as clinical sign. Spontaneous resolution of pseudocysts occurs in most of the patients and symptomatic patients can be managed by intervention by open/endoscopic internal drainage with or without pancreatic stenting and external drainage should be reserved for infected pseudocysts.

References

1. Grace PA and Williamson RC. Modern management of pancreatic pseudocysts. *Br J Surg* 1993; 80:573-581.

2. Bradley EL, Clements JL, Jr., Gonzalez AC. The natural history of pancreatic pseudocysts: a unified concept of management. *Am J Surg*. 1979; 137: 135- 141
3. Tuula Kiviluoto, MD; Leena Kivisaari, MD; Eero Kivilaakso, MD et al - Pseudocysts in Chronic Pancreatitis: Surgical Results in 102 Consecutive Patients. *Arch Surg*. 1989; 124(2):240-243.
4. Fitzgerald PJ. Medical anecdotes concerning some diseases of the pancreas. *The pancreas*. 1980: 17-19.
5. Yeo CJ, Sarr MG: Cystic and pseudocystic diseases of the pancreas. *Curr Probl Surg*. 1994; 3:167-243.
6. Rosato EL, Sonnenday CJ, Lillmoe KD, Yeo CJ. Pseudocyst and other complications of pancreatitis. In: Shackelford's surgery of alimentary tract. Charles J Yeo, Danies T. Dempsey, Andrews Khein, et al. 7th Ed., Saunders. Elsevier. 2013: 144-1167.
7. Cannon JW, Callery MP, and Vollmer CM JR. "Diagnosis and management of pancreatic pseudo cysts: what is the evidence?" *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*. 2009; 209(3):385-393.
8. Bradley EL III. "A clinically based classification system for acute pancreatitis: summary of the International Symposium on Acute Pancreatitis, Atlanta, Ga, September 11 through 13, 1992," *Archives of Surgery*. 1993; 128(5):586-590.
9. Samokhvalov AV, Rehm J, Roerecke M. Alcohol consumption as a risk factor for acute and chronic pancreatitis: a systematic review and a series of meta-analyses. *EBioMedicine*. 2015; 2(12):1996- 2002.
10. Habashi S, Draganov PV. Pancreatic pseudocyst. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2009; 15(1):38.
11. Koide T, Saraya T, Nakajima A, Kurai D, Ishii H, Goto H. A 54-year-old man with an uncommon cause of left pleural effusion. *Chest*. 2012; 141(2):560-3.
12. Habashi S, Draganov PV. Pancreatic pseudocyst. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2009; 15:38-47.
13. Usatoff V, Brancatisano R, Williamson RC. Operative treatment of pseudocysts in patients with chronic pancreatitis. *British J S*. 2000; 87(11):1494- 9.
14. Cannon JW, Callery MP, Vollmer CM. Diagnosis and management of pancreas pseudocysts: what is the evidence? *J Am Coll Surg*. 2009; 209:385-93.
15. Laddha V, Tubachi P, Shenoy KR. Pseudocyst of Pancreas: A Clinical Study. *IOSR J Dent Med Sci*. 2015; 14(10):101-5.